

THE INFLUENCE OF LEAD ON THE GROWTH AND DEVELOPMENT OF ALFALFA ON SIEROZEM SOILS OF THE SOUTHERN REGIONS OF KAZAKHSTAN

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ABSTRACT

The article presents the results of laboratory and field experiments on the study of lead migration in the soil-plant system. The research was carried out using sierozem soils of the southern regions of Kazakhstan, alfalfa (*Medicago L.*) was used as a plant for the study. During the growing season, alfalfa was cut twice. The data obtained indicate the absence of identical patterns, i.e. during the first cutting, there is an intensive accumulation of lead in the ground part of alfalfa, and during the second cutting, Pb accumulation is observed in the root part, only a small amount of lead passes into the ground part.

The chemical content of nutrients and other substances in grown alfalfa - fiber, protein, carotene, carbohydrates and ash - has been determined. The highest content of nutrients was found in the ground part of alfalfa of the 1st cutting.

Keywords: heavy metals, lead, alfalfa, sierozem, phytoremediation.

Introduction

For heavy metals, soil is considered a major acceptor in the cycle of chemical pollutants in the biosphere [1]. The soil constantly interacts with other ecological systems – the atmosphere, hydrosphere, vegetation and is an important source of heavy metals entering the human body [2].

The volume of research work on the detection of heavy metals in the soil is very large. The sources of heavy metals entering the soil are considered in detail and the total content of a number of metals is studied [3-5].

The concentration of heavy metals affects the properties of the soil. Soils with a heavy granulometric composition contain high concentrations of heavy metals, while sandy and clay soils accumulate them in small quantities. The acid-base properties of the soil have a significant effect. Under acidic conditions, the insoluble part of the heavy metal fraction transforms into soluble compounds, thereby increasing the concentration of heavy metals in acidic soil [6].

The accumulation of heavy metals in the soil reduces its fertility, microbiological activity, plant growth and development, as well as the quality of crop production [7]. Normal (background) concentrations of heavy metals in the soil can be regulated by plants through the root system. At high concentrations, the protective and regulatory mechanisms of plants cannot resist the entry of heavy metals into vegetative organs [8].

The urgency of the problem of reducing the influence of heavy metals on soil toxicity is due to the fact that the mechanisms of natural self-purification of these pollutants are practically absent, since during migration

they change only the shape or amount of their location [9].

Soil is one of the first links in the biogeochemical food chain and is the initial stage of heavy metal migration in the soil-plant-animal-food-human system [10]. Therefore, special attention is paid to the identification of the inactivating ability of mobile forms of heavy metals entering the soil, as well as to the study of methods regulating and controlling the flow of toxic substances from the soil into plants [11].

In world practice, plants are used as one of the widespread methods of cleaning the soil from heavy metals. There is no single phytoremediation technology, since the choice of a particular plant species directly depends on the geographical location of the cultivated soil [12].

In practice, only two chemical reactions are used to restore the fertility of soil contaminated with heavy metals (leaching of metals and conversion to a slow-moving form) [13]. However, attempts to rehabilitate contaminated soil by physical and chemical methods often do not give the desired results [14].

Phytoremediation, which uses the combined metabolic potential of microorganisms and plants, plays a special role in cleaning the mobile soil layer from toxic substances [15-17]. The use of biological methods of soil restoration and purification ensures environmental safety and economic efficiency [18]. In this regard, it is very important to carry out the process of restoring contaminated soil using various plants.

Currently, the problem of reducing contamination of plant products with heavy metals, especially lead compounds, is acute. Increased lead content in soils

causes plants to delay growth, damage to the root system, and leaf chlorosis. The phytotoxicity of lead manifests itself in an inhibitory effect on photosynthesis, impaired transpiration, CO₂ fixation, and changes in the permeability of cell membranes. In this regard, finding optimal ways to regulate the mechanisms of physiological and biochemical processes in plants is one of the urgent tasks.

The purpose of our work is to study the behavior of lead in the sierozem-alfalfa system and to select optimal conditions for obtaining environmentally friendly forage grasses.

Objects and methods of research

The plots of land under the influence of waste from a lead plant and landfills of solid household waste

in the Turkestan region were selected as objects of research. As a control, sierozem soils from places unpolluted with heavy metals were used, in the soils of which the average content of humic substances is ~ 1.7% (0-40 cm). These lands are actively used for sowing legume forage grasses, in particular alfalfa. Alfalfa (*Medicago L.*) is a cosmopolitan plant species that grows in all climatic zones and on all types of soils. It is widely used as a forage crop. This crop has a developed root system, thus, along with enriching the soil with nitrogen, it improves its structure. The model experiments were carried out using wooden boxes without a bottom with a height of 50 cm and a size of 50x60 cm (Fig. 1).

Figure 1 – Model experiments with alfalfa grown in soil contaminated with lead

The determination of heavy metals in soil and in plant material (after dry salinization) was carried out by the voltammetric method using the Ta-Lab device.

The determination of the content of nutrients of protein, fiber, carbohydrates, carotene and other components was carried out using well-known classical methods [19-20].

Results and discussion

The lead content in the studied soils was many times higher than the standard value (MPC = 32 mg/kg) applicable to soils in Kazakhstan (Table 1). Based on the results of the fractional composition, it was revealed that the main content of humic acids and lead is concentrated in fractions of < 0.05 mm. The accumulation of lead in fine particles poses a threat to public health. This is due to the fact that strong winds are very common in the study areas, which carry lead and other toxicants with fine particles over long distances.

Table 1

Gross content of fine particles, humus, lead in the studied soils (numerator) and in their fractions (denominator) taken from a depth of 0-40 cm)

Soil sampling sites at a distance of 250 m from the source of contamination (№)	Content		
	fractions of less than 0.05 mm, in % of absolutely dry soil	humus, %	lead, mg/kg
Control uncontaminated soil (№ 1)	42,5±0,9	<u>1,7±0,2</u> 1,1±0,2	<u>10,1±0,5</u> 8,0±0,1
Landfill of lead plant waste (№ 2)	53,2±0,5	<u>1,2±0,2</u> 0,9±0,02	<u>210,7±0,5</u> 126,6±0,3
Landfill of lead plant waste (№ 3)	54,0±0,5	<u>1,3±0,3</u> 0,6±0,02	<u>199,8±0,5</u> 130,8±0,3
Landfill of the city of Turkestan (№ 4)	55,6±0,3	<u>1,2±0,3</u> 0,7±0,02	<u>148,6±0,5</u> 129,8±0,3

During cultivation, alfalfa crops were watered with water and aqueous solutions of vermicompost. The results of the experiments are presented in Table 2. It follows from the data obtained during the experiments that the translocation content of lead in the plant depends on its content in the soil, i.e. with an increase in the level of soil contamination, the concentration of Pb in alfalfa increases. At the same time, on the contrary, the yield decreases significantly. When watering with vermicompost solutions, both at the first and second cutting, the amount of lead transferred to the plant decreases. The lead content in alfalfa of the 2nd cutting

when watered with a 50% worm tea solution did not exceed the standard level (permissible levels in forage plants of lead - 0.5 mg / kg). This can be explained by the binding of lead ions with humic acids to form insoluble humates (HA) and fulvates (FA) in the soil system based on the following reactions:

Table 2

№ soil samples	Initial Pb content, g/kg soil	1 cut		2 cut			
		when watering the soil					
		with water	with a worm tea solution		with water	with a worm tea solution	
			25 %	50 %		25 %	50 %
Control (№1)	10,1±0,5	1,7	0,3	0,1	0,9	0,7	0,2
№ 2	210,7±0,5	4,2	1,7	0,6	3,3	0,8	0,3
№ 3	199,8±0,5	5,0	2,2	0,5	2,9	0,5	0,3
№ 4	148,6±0,5	3,5	2,5	0,7	2,8	0,6	0,1

Based on the analysis of the results of the chemical composition of alfalfa, the dependence of the content of carotene, protein, fiber, carbohydrates on the order of mowing was revealed. The highest content of the above components is observed at the 2nd cutting (Table 3).

Table 3

Chemical composition of the ground part of alfalfa in terms of dry matter (watering with 50 % worm tea solution)

Order of cuttings	Carotene, mg/kg	Content in %			Ash, g
		protein	fiber	carbohydrates	
1st	48,4±0,3	23,2±0,5	21,0±0,6	17,1±0,5	8,1±0,5
2nd	50,6±0,3	29,0±0,5	25,8±0,6	17,8±0,5	7,2±0,4

Conclusions

In the first cutting, it was found that the amount of lead transferred to the alfalfa plant in common sierozem increases with increasing metal concentration, and the yield of the plant decreases slightly. At the same place, it was found that alfalfa plays the role of a battery accumulating ecotoxicants.

In the 2nd cutting of alfalfa, previously undetected properties appeared when the role of the studied heavy metal as a battery decreased slightly, and the amount of Pb transferred to the upper part of the plant decreased sharply. It has been proved that the amount of heavy metals in the aboveground part of alfalfa (first cutting) grown on sierozem contaminated with lead exceeds the regulatory level. Thus, it was established that the first cut of alfalfa grown on polluted sierozem cannot be used as feed.

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